

online repository file 5. Effects of incretin mimetic drug treatment as therapeutic intervention model. (A) Experimental protocol. Incretin mimetic drugs and the vehicle were administered subcutaneously on day 3, 6, and 9. Intranasal challenge of 8 μg (protein amount)/80 μL phosphate buffered saline (PBS) of *Alternaria* extract (Alt-Ext) occurred on day 0, 3, 6, and 9. The BALF, whole lung, and serum were harvested 24 h after the last Alt-Ext-challenge on day 10. (B-I) Lung homogenates were prepared to measure the protein expression of IL-5, IL-6, IL-13, IL-33, CCL11 (eotaxin), CCL17 (TARC), CCL22 (MDC), and CCL24 (eotaxin-2) by ELISA (n=6-7). (J-M) BALF were harvested 24 h after the last Alt-Ext-challenge to evaluate cell differentials, (J) macrophages, (K) eosinophils, (L) lymphocytes, and (M) neutrophils. (n=6-7) All results and shown as mean \pm S.D. * $P < 0.05$. ** $P < 0.01$. *** $P < 0.001$.